

Supplementary material for “Spatially explicit model to disentangle effects of environment on annual fish reproduction”

Ilaria Pia¹, Elina Numminen¹, Lari Veneranta², and Jarno Vanhatalo^{1,3}

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Faculty of Science, University of Helsinki

²Natural Resources Institute Finland

³Organismal and Evolutionary Biology Research Programme, Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences, University of Helsinki

1 Prior distributions

1.1 Priors for covariate effects

We gave covariate effects, $\bar{\beta}, \beta, \bar{b}$, weakly informative priors that shrink unnecessary covariate effects towards zero by imposing them a Group Inverse-Gamma Gamma Shrinkage prior (Boss et al., 2023). For each of the three regression components, we grouped together the coefficients for linear and quadratic effects of a covariate, so that we got $g = 1, \dots, 7$ groups with $p = 1, 2$ elements. For example, the group inverse-gamma gamma prior for each regression coefficient of the spawner density model was defined as $\beta_{gp} | \tau, \gamma_g, \psi_{gp} \sim N(0, \tau^2 \gamma_g^2 \psi_{gp}^2)$, where the variance parameter priors were: $\gamma_g \sim \text{Gamma}(0.5, 1)$, $\psi_{gp} \sim \text{InvGamma}(0.5, 1)$, $\tau \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, \sigma_\tau)$ and $\sigma_\tau \sim \text{Student-}t(4, 0, 1)$. The same distributional assumptions were used to build the Group Inverse-Gamma Gamma priors for suitability and proliferation rate regression coefficients as well.

1.2 Priors for other parameters

Prior information on density-independent survival and fish egg production exists for defining informative prior for the log maximum proliferation rate, \bar{a} and the effect of fish weight on it, $f(w)$. Since the maximum proliferation rate parameter $a_{i,t}$ represents the same quantity (i.e., the slope of the reproduction curve at small spawner density) in the density-independent, the Ricker, and Beverton-Holt model (equations (4), (5), and (6) in the main manuscript), we used the same prior for \bar{a} for all these three models. Lehtonen (1981) provides data on the relationship between whitefish weight and egg production in the Gulf of Bothnia. Good regression fit for this data was obtained with a linear model, $\text{eggs} = h \times w$, resulting in posterior mean $\hat{h} = 26614$ eggs/kg and 95% credible interval from 25658 to 27566 (with vague prior on h) and high explanatory power (Bayesian R-squared 0.9904 with 95% confidence interval from 0.9877 to 0.9913; Figure A.1). Veneranta et al. (2013) and Freeberg et al. (1990) found that at most 25% of whitefish eggs survived to larval stage in experimental cages in the Bothnian Sea and at most 7% of eggs survived in the Great Lakes, North America. Hence, we used $27566 \times 0.28 \approx 7450$ as the prior 97.5'th percentile (i.e., *a priori* maximum estimate) for the maximum proliferation rate of one kg whitefish. Furthermore, we assumed that on average a spawning whitefish must produce a minimum of the order of ten larvae to ensure sustainable renewal of whitefish stock (note larvae are still subject to high mortality).

Since whitefish in the Gulf of Bothnia weight in average 0.2 kg, the egg survival must be at minimum of the order of 10^{-3} for this to hold, corresponding to maximum proliferation rate of the order of 100 for one kg whitefish. Hence, we defined $f(w) = \log(w)$ and gave \bar{a} a Gaussian prior that matches the prior central 95% credible interval of [100,7450] for the maximum proliferation rate in average conditions within the larvae sampling sites. This would correspond to prior $\bar{a} \sim N(6.67, 1)$ if all covariates were standardized (mean zero and sd one). However, since we restricted the quadratic effects of the standardized environmental covariates to be negative, the average contribution from these second order terms is not zero but it is the sum of their regression coefficients' prior medians. Accounting for this quadratic regression coefficients' contribution resulted in a Gaussian prior with mean 9.145 and standard deviation 1 for \bar{a} . Independent prior information on expected spawner density or suitability were not available, so we gave the intercept terms $\bar{\alpha}$ and α weakly informative Gaussian priors. When setting these priors, we applied similar restricted quadratic effects correction as for \bar{a} so that, under average conditions, the suitability is centered around 0.5 with standard deviation 1/4 and the log spawner density at 0 with standard deviation two. This resulted in weakly informative priors $\bar{\alpha} \sim N(2.475, 1)$ and $\alpha \sim N(2.475, 4)$.

We derived a weakly informative prior for the density-dependent mortality parameter (b) based on the observed egg densities in whitefish spawning grounds and prior estimates on whitefish population doubling time. Veneranta and Harjunpää (2017) found that the whitefish egg density varied from 12 to 110 eggs per m^2 in different bottom types in river Kokemäenjoki (a river pouring to the Gulf of Bothnia). Based on the average egg production of whitefish, these numbers correspond to $12/26614 \approx 4.5 \times 10^{-4}$ and $110/26614 \approx 4.1 \times 10^{-3}$ kg/ m^2 of spawning (female) whitefish. According to FishBase database (Froese and Pauly, 2023) the whitefish minimum population doubling time ranges from 1.4 to 4.4 years, corresponding to intrinsic growth rates of $\log(2)/1.4 = 0.5$ and $\log(2)/4.4 = 0.16$. In the Ricker model, the parameter b is the same as intrinsic growth rate divided by the carrying capacity. If the whitefish populations were at their carrying capacity, and only spawning-to-larvae time processes would contribute to density-dependent mortality, the observed egg densities would, thus, correspond to density-dependent mortality parameters of the order of $10^2, \dots, 10^3$. However, since all whitefish populations within the Gulf of Bothnia experience spawning time fishing, the observed numbers are very likely smaller than what they would be if populations were at their natural carrying capacity. Moreover, at full population level, density-dependent mortality happens also after larvae have hatched. Hence, the realistic order of magnitude of b in our model is very likely less than 10^2 . For this reason, we gave b a weakly informative prior using a half Student-t distribution, with mean parameter zero, scale 20 and four degrees of freedom, $\nu = 4$, which implies that most of the prior mass for b is near zero and with 99% prior probability b is below 100. We used the same prior in the Beverton-Holt model.

There was no prior information on the rest of the parameters so we gave them weakly informative priors. For the fisheries catch rate we gave prior of $\lambda \sim \text{Gamma}(2, 10)$, restricted to $\lambda > 10^{-4}$ to ensure non-zero catch probability, which corresponds to prior mean of 0.2 and prior 95% confidence interval of (0.024,0.557) for the probability that a fish was caught with average fishing effort over all the regions during the study period. For the larvae abundance overdispersion parameter we gave a prior of $r \sim \text{Gamma}(1, 0.1)$, which allows high overdispersion for larvae counts since it corresponds to prior mean of ten, 60% probability that r is smaller than ten, and a prior 95% confidence interval of (0.253,36.889). For the variance parameter of the spatiotemporal random effect (σ_δ) we gave a half Student-t(4,0,1) prior and for the length scale parameter (l) a log-Gaussian prior with mean 4.2 and standard deviation 1. The latter implies that the prior 95% confidence interval is approximately between 10 and 500 km, and the average length scale is 100 km.

Figure A.1: (A) Number of eggs produced by whitefish (dots) increases linearly as the weight of the fish increases (the linear model fit represented by straight line). (B) The weight of whitefish (triangles and squares) decreases from south to northern (the linear model fit represented by straight line), and the decrease is steeper for female than male whitefish.

2 Identifiability of the model parameters

Here we analyze whether the parameters of the joint observation model (Equation (12) in the main manuscript) are identifiable or not with data available to us. We follow the classical definition of identifiability by which a statistical model $p = \{p_\theta : \theta \in \Theta\}$, with parameter space Θ is identifiable if the mapping $\theta \rightarrow p_\theta$ is one-to-one. That is, $p_{\theta_1} = p_{\theta_2} \Rightarrow \theta_1 = \theta_2$. First, we prove the identifiability of the parameters for the zero-inflated and hurdle negative binomial models and after that we continue the analysis of the full observation model.

2.1 Identifiability of the zero-inflated negative binomial model

Li (2012) proved that the zero-inflated Poisson model is identifiable for the parameters of the occurrence probability and the intensity function. Our proof for the zero-inflated negative binomial model follows their approach - the only difference being the extra consideration for the overdispersion parameter missing from the Poisson distribution.

Using the notation of the rest of the paper (and setting $V = 1$), the zero-inflated negative binomial model (Equation (7) in the main manuscript) is

$$p(y|\theta, \tilde{\eta}, r) = (1 - \theta)\mathbb{1}_{y=0} + \theta \frac{\Gamma(r+y)}{y!\Gamma(r)} \left(\frac{r}{r+\tilde{\eta}}\right)^r \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}}{r+\tilde{\eta}}\right)^y. \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{y=0}$ is an indicator function returning one if $y = 0$ and zero otherwise.

Lemma 1. *Let x be a continuous covariate in the design space $\mathbb{X} = [d_0, d_1]$, where $-\infty < d_0 < d_1 < \infty$. The zero-inflated negative binomial model in (1) is identifiable when $\theta(x)$ and $\tilde{\eta}(x)$ are unspecified smooth functions of x .*

Proof. To prove the identifiability of the zero-inflated negative binomial model, we need to show that $p(y|\theta(x), \tilde{\eta}(x), r) = p(y|\theta^*(x), \tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)$ if and only if $\theta(x) = \theta^*(x)$, $\tilde{\eta}(x) = \tilde{\eta}^*(x)$, and $r = r^*$ for $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and $y = 0, 1, \dots$. The "if" part is clearly true so we show the "only if" part.

Assume that $p(y|\theta(x), \tilde{\eta}(x), r) = p(y|\theta^*(x), \tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)$ for all $y = 0, 1, \dots$. By putting Equation (1) into the left and right hand side of this equality, and rearranging the terms, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Gamma(r^* + y)}{\Gamma(r^*)} \left(\frac{r^*}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \right)^{r^*} \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \right)^y \\ &= (1 - c(x)) y! \mathbb{1}_{y=0} + c(x) \frac{\Gamma(r + y)}{\Gamma(r)} \left(\frac{r}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} \right)^r \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} \right)^y, \quad y = 0, 1, \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $c(x) = \theta(x)/\theta^*(x)$. By fixing $y = 2$ and solving for $c(x)$ we get

$$c(x) = \frac{\Gamma(r)}{\Gamma(r + 2)} \left(\frac{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)}{r} \right)^r \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} \right)^2 \frac{\Gamma(r^* + 2)}{\Gamma(r^*)} \left(\frac{r^*}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \right)^{r^*} \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \right)^2. \quad (3)$$

Next, by fixing $y = 1$ in (2), putting (3) into it, and simplifying, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(r^* + 1) &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(r + 2)} \frac{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)}{\tilde{\eta}(x)} \Gamma(r^* + 2) \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \Gamma(r + 1) \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} &= \frac{r^* + 1}{r + 1} \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Similarly, by fixing $y = 3$ in (2) and putting (3) into it, we get

$$(r^* + 2) \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} = (r + 2) \frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)}. \quad (5)$$

Now, by combining (4) with (5) gives us $r^* = r$ and, by putting this into (4), we get that $\tilde{\eta}(x) = \tilde{\eta}^*(x)$. Finally, by applying these two equalities to (2) and rearranging, we get

$$c(x) = \frac{\theta(x)}{\theta^*(x)} = 1 \Rightarrow \theta(x) = \theta^*(x), \quad (6)$$

which completes the proof. \square

2.2 Identifiability of the Hurdle negative binomial model

Our proof for the Hurdle negative binomial model follows the same approach as for the zero-inflated negative binomial. Using the notation of the rest of the paper (and setting $V = 1$), the hurdle negative binomial model (Equation (7) in the main manuscript) is

$$p(y|\theta, \tilde{\eta}, r) = (1 - \theta) \mathbb{1}_{y=0} + \left(\theta \frac{\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}, r)}{1 - \text{NB}(0|\tilde{\eta}, r)} \right) \mathbb{1}_{y>0} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{y \in S}$ is an indicator function returning one if $y \in S$ and zero otherwise. While $\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}, r) = \frac{\Gamma(r+y)}{y! \Gamma(r)} \left(\frac{r}{r+\tilde{\eta}} \right)^r \left(\frac{\tilde{\eta}}{r+\tilde{\eta}} \right)^y$.

Lemma 2. *Let x be a continuous covariate in the design space $\mathbb{X} = [d_0, d_1]$, where $-\infty < d_0 < d_1 < \infty$. The Hurdle negative binomial model in (7) is identifiable when $\theta(x)$ and $\tilde{\eta}(x)$ are unspecified smooth functions of x .*

Proof. To prove the identifiability of the hurdle negative binomial model, we need to show that $p(y|\theta(x), \tilde{\eta}(x), r) = p(y|\theta^*(x), \tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)$ if and only if $\theta(x) = \theta^*(x)$, $\tilde{\eta}(x) = \tilde{\eta}^*(x)$, and $r = r^*$ for $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and $y = 0, 1, \dots$. The "if" part is clearly true so we show the "only if" part.

Assume that $p(y|\theta(x), \tilde{\eta}(x), r) = p(y|\theta^*(x), \tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)$ for all $y = 0, 1, \dots$. Then, by fixing $y = 0$ in Equation 7, we get

$$1 - \theta(x) = 1 - \theta^*(x) \implies \theta(x) = \theta^*(x). \quad (8)$$

By putting Equation (7) into the left and right hand side of the assumed equality of probability mass, and rearranging the terms, we obtain

$$(1 - c(x))\mathbb{1}_{y=0} + \frac{\theta(x)}{\theta^*(x)} \frac{\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)}{1 - \text{NB}(0|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)} \mathbb{1}_{y>0} = \frac{\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)}{1 - \text{NB}(0|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)} \mathbb{1}_{y>0}. \quad (9)$$

By Equation 8 $\theta(x)/\theta^*(x) = 1$ so that

$$\frac{\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)}{\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)} = \frac{1 - \text{NB}(0|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)}{1 - \text{NB}(0|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)} \quad (10)$$

for all $y \geq 0$. The right hand side of Equation 10 is independent of y , hence setting $y = 1$ and $y = 2$ in the left hand side (LHS) of Equation 10 and equating the two ratios, we have:

$$\frac{\text{NB}(1|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)}{\text{NB}(1|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)} = \frac{\text{NB}(2|\tilde{\eta}^*(x), r^*)}{\text{NB}(2|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)} \quad (11)$$

and using the Gamma function property $\Gamma(n+1) = n\Gamma(n)$, we obtain:

$$\frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} = \frac{r^* + 1}{r + 1} \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)}. \quad (12)$$

Similarly, by setting $y = 2$ and $y = 3$ we have

$$\frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} = \frac{r^* + 2}{r + 2} \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r^* + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)}. \quad (13)$$

Then RHS of Equation 12 equals RHS of 13 and gives:

$$\frac{r^* + 2}{r + 2} = \frac{r^* + 1}{r + 1} \implies r = r^* \quad (14)$$

Putting $r = r^*$ in Equation 12, we get:

$$\frac{\tilde{\eta}(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}(x)} = \frac{\tilde{\eta}^*(x)}{r + \tilde{\eta}^*(x)} \implies \tilde{\eta}(x) = \tilde{\eta}^*(x), \quad (15)$$

that completes the proof. \square

2.3 Identifiability of the full observation model

For notational simplicity, but without loss of generality, we prove the identifiability theorem by considering only one covariate for the functions $\theta(x)$, $\eta(x)$ and $a(x)$. This implies also that we remove the effect of fish weight on the maximum proliferation rate function $a(x)$ in the following treatment. With zero-inflated formulation for the larvae counts, the full observation model (Equation (12) in the main manuscript) can be written as

$$p(C^{(\text{kg})}|\eta(X), \theta(X), \lambda, \sigma_\epsilon^2)p(y|\eta(x), \theta(x), a(x), b, r) = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\nu+1}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\nu}{2})\sqrt{\nu\pi}\sigma} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\nu} \frac{(C^{(\text{kg})} - \mu(X))^2}{\sigma^2}\right)^{-(\nu+1)/2} [(1 - \theta(x))\mathbb{1}_{y=0} + \theta(x)\text{NB}(y|\tilde{\eta}(x), r)] \quad (16)$$

where we have denoted by $X \in \mathbb{X}^{|S_j|}$ a vector of covariate values in $|S_j|$ mesh grid cells which the fisheries catch corresponds to, by $\theta(X)$ and $\eta(X)$ vectors of suitability probabilities and spawner densities constructed by applying $\theta(\cdot)$ and $\eta(\cdot)$ elementwise to X and by $\mu(X) = \frac{\omega}{\phi} \sum_{i \in S_j} \left(e^{E\lambda\theta(x_i)/\sum_{i \in S_j} \theta(x_i)} - 1\right) A_i\theta(x_i)\eta(x_i)$. Moreover, $\tilde{\eta}(x)$ is a function of $\eta(x)$, $a(x)$, and b as defined by the density-independent model, the Ricker model, or the Beverton-Holt

this equality as

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\sigma}{c_3(x,y)}\right)^{2/\nu+1} - \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{c_3^*(x,y)}\right)^{2/\nu+1} - \left(\frac{\mu(X)^2}{\nu(c_3(x,y)\sigma^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}} - \frac{\mu^*(X)^2}{\nu(c_3^*(x,y)(\sigma^*)^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}}\right) \\ - \left(\frac{1}{\nu(c_3(x,y)\sigma^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}} - \frac{1}{\nu(c_3^*(x,y)(\sigma^*)^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}}\right) (C^{(\text{kg})})^2 \\ - \left(\frac{\mu(X)}{\nu(c_3(x,y)\sigma^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}} - \frac{\mu^*(X)}{\nu(c_3^*(x,y)(\sigma^*)^\nu)^{2/(\nu+1)}}\right) 2C^{(\text{kg})} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Now, in order for the equality to hold for all $C^{(\text{kg})} \in \mathfrak{R}$, $y = 0, 1, \dots$, $x \in \mathbb{X}$, and $X \in \mathbb{X}^{|S_j|}$ all of the above lines have to be zero. Hence, from the second line we obtain $c_3(x,y)\sigma^\nu = c_3^*(x,y)(\sigma^*)^\nu$. Combining this with the third line we get that $\mu(X) = \mu^*(X)$. For last combining these with the first line, and opening $c_3(x,y)$, we can show that $\theta(x) = \theta^*(x)$ and $\sigma = \sigma^*$.

By now, we have shown that the model is identifiable for r , σ , $\theta(x)$, $\tilde{\eta}(x)$, and $\mu(X)$. However, it remains to examine whether the model is identifiable for λ , $\eta(x)$, $a(x)$, and, in case of Ricker and Beverton-Holt models, b . We treat these three models in turn.

Density-independent model: Since, the full model is identifiable for $\mu(X)$, $\theta(x)$ and $\tilde{\eta}(x)$ the model is identifiable for λ , $\eta(x)$, and $a(x)$ when

$$\begin{cases} \sum (e^{E\lambda\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1) A_i\theta(x_i)\eta(x_i) & = \sum (e^{E\lambda^*\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1) A_i\theta(x_i)\eta^*(x_i) \\ a(x)\eta(x) & = a^*(x)\eta^*(x) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

if and only if $a(x) = a^*(x)$, $\lambda = \lambda^*$ and $\eta(x) = \eta^*(x)$ for all $x_i \in \mathbb{X}$. From the first line of (20) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i \in S_j} \theta(x_i) \left(\left(e^{E\lambda\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) \eta(x_i) - \left(e^{E\lambda^*\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) \eta^*(x_i) \right) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{i \in S_j} \theta(x_i) \left(\left(e^{E\lambda\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) e^\alpha e^{\beta x_i} - \left(e^{E\lambda^*\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) e^{\alpha^*} e^{\beta^* x_i} \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Since exponential functions are linearly independent and since the multiplier of the above exponential functions are positive, the above equality holds only if $\beta = \beta^*$ and if

$$\left(e^{E\lambda\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) e^\alpha = \left(e^{E\lambda^*\theta(x_i)/\sum\theta(x_i)} - 1 \right) e^{\alpha^*} \quad (22)$$

Hence, the model is identifiable for β . This, together with the second line of (20), implies that

$$\frac{\eta(x)}{\eta^*(x)} = e^{\alpha - \alpha^*} = \frac{a^*(x)}{a(x)} = e^{\bar{a}^* - \bar{a} + (\bar{b}^* - \bar{b})x}. \quad (23)$$

For this to hold, we must have $\bar{b}^* = \bar{b}$, so that the model is identifiable up to a constant of proportionality for η and $a(x)$. However, the model is not identifiable for λ , nor the scale parameters α and \bar{a} . To see this, we can define $e^{\alpha^*} = \kappa e^\alpha$, $a^*(x) = a(x)/\kappa$ and $\lambda^* = \log(e^{E\lambda/\sum\theta_i/\kappa} - 1/\kappa + 1) \sum\theta_i/(E\theta_i)$ in which case the equation (20) holds as well. However, if we fix λ , α or \bar{a} , it follows from (22) and (23) that the other two parameters are identifiable.

Ricker model: With the Ricker model, we can proceed similarly as in the density-independent model and use the first line of (20) to show that the model is identifiable for β . Then, the second line of (20) is replaced with

$$a(x)\eta(x)e^{-b\eta(x)} = a^*(x)\eta^*(x)e^{-b^*\eta^*(x)} \quad (24)$$

which gives us

$$\log(a(x)e^\alpha) - be^\alpha e^{\beta x} = \log(a^*(x)e^{\alpha^*}) - b^*e^{\alpha^*}e^{\beta x} \quad (25)$$

$$\bar{a}^* - \bar{a} + \alpha^* - \alpha + (\bar{b}^* - \bar{b})x + (be^\alpha - b^*e^{\alpha^*})e^{\beta x} = 0 \quad (26)$$

For the above to hold, we must have that $b^*e^{\alpha^*} = be^\alpha$, $\bar{b}^* = \bar{b}$ and $\bar{a}^* + \alpha^* = \bar{a} + \alpha$. These imply that the model is again identifiable up to a constant of proportionality for $\eta(x)$ and $a(x)$ but, through similar argument as in the density-independent model, it is not identifiable for the scale parameters α and \bar{a} , the density-dependent parameter b , nor the fisheries mortality rate λ . However, similarly as in the density-independent model, if we fix b , α , \bar{a} , or λ , the model is identifiable for the rest of the parameters.

Beverton-Holt model: With the Beverton-Holt model, we can again use the first line of (20) to show that the model is identifiable for β . Then, the second line of (20) is replaced with

$$\frac{a(x)\eta(x)}{1 + b\eta(x)} = \frac{a(x)^*\eta^*(x)}{1 + b^*\eta^*(x)} \quad (27)$$

which gives us

$$\bar{a} + \alpha - \bar{a}^* - \alpha^* + (\bar{b} - \bar{b}^*)x + \log\left(\frac{1 + b^*e^{\alpha^* + \beta x}}{1 + be^{\alpha + \beta x}}\right) = 0 \quad (28)$$

For the above to hold for all x , we must have that $\bar{b} = \bar{b}^*$, $be^\alpha = b^*e^{\alpha^*}$ and $\bar{a} + \alpha = \bar{a}^* + \alpha^*$. These imply again that the model is identifiable up to a constant of proportionality for $\eta(x)$ and $a(x)$ but, through similar argument as in the density-independent model, it is not identifiable for the scale parameters α and \bar{a} , the density-dependent parameter b , nor the fisheries mortality rate λ . However, similarly as in the density-independent model and the Ricker model, if we fix b , α , \bar{a} , or λ , the model is identifiable for the rest of the parameters.

With the hurdle formulation for the larvae counts, the proof is analogous. □

3 Details of the simulation study

3.1 Construction of simulated data

In each simulated data, we defined the study area as a unit square covered by three simulated environmental covariates (on a regular 50×50 lattice), four equally sized fisheries regions (common to all simulations), and 100 larvae sampling locations randomly distributed over the area. For each of the simulated data set, we first simulated environmental covariates, fishing efforts, and the larval sampling locations. The environmental covariates were sampled from a multivariate Gaussian distribution, with mean $(3, 0, 3)$ and covariance matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.8 \\ 0 & 0.8 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$, so that the first covariate is independent of the others and follows a spatial gradient, while the second and third covariates are highly correlated. The fishing efforts were sampled uniformly from the set of integers between 10 and 100, the larvae water sampling volumes were selected randomly from values between 1 and 10, while the average weights, in kg, for each region were sampled from a $\text{Gamma}(4, 20)$. Next, for each simulated data set, we sampled the first and second order environmental covariate effects from i.i.d. Gaussian distributions. In scenarios 1 and 2 we used Gaussians with mean 0 and variance equal to 2, for linear effects, and half standard Gaussians for quadratic effects. In scenario 3 we sampled the linear covariates effects for spawner density and maximum proliferation rate from a bivariate Gaussian Distribution, with correlation equal to 0.85, while suitability effects were sampled

Table A.1: Posterior mean and 95% credible interval of the main parameters of the SDM and of the spatially explicit Ricker, Beverton-Holt, and density-independent larval production models under the zero-inflated formulation.

SDM	Posterior mean (95% credible interval)			
	Ricker	Beverton-Holt	Density-independent	
σ_ϵ	NA	0.4112 (0.1389 , 0.6940)	0.4034 (0.1352 , 0.7032)	0.4182 (0.1469 , 0.6998)
σ_δ	2.705 (1.3922 , 4.6055)	2.8372 (1.2877 , 4.8813)	2.6219 (0.993 , 4.7465)	2.6581 (1.0606 , 4.9048)
$\bar{\alpha}$	2.5277 (2.0588 , 3.0018)	2.5166 (2.0002 , 2.9941)	2.5042 (2.0564 , 2.965)	2.5169 (2.0761 , 2.9915)
\bar{a}	7.1924 (5.1958 , 9.2665)	9.2615 (7.7631 , 10.8982)	8.9324 (6.9696 , 10.9226)	8.9204 (6.9418 , 10.9255)
r	0.207 (0.1629 , 0.2659)	0.1968 (0.1535 , 0.2559)	0.1957 (0.1528 , 0.2528)	0.1963 (0.1521 , 0.2517)
l	287.7981 (45.3198 , 823.1718)	1108.5582 (212.7904 , 2980.6661)	985.2251 (132.6245 , 3099.2276)	1002.6956 (165.7304 , 3068.6409)
α	NA	-0.2925 (-3.5506 , 3.3443)	-0.4883 (-3.7327 , 3.2525)	-0.4725 (-3.7268 , 3.0977)
λ	NA	0.0058 (0.0011 , 0.0246)	0.0048 (2e-04 , 0.0223)	0.0050 (3e-04 , 0.0250)
b	NA	19.2127 (0.9413 , 68.9113)	19.5040 (0.7373 , 65.4522)	NA

as before. We sampled the remaining model parameters from their prior distributions (table 2 in the main manuscript) and calculated the suitability, the spawner density and the maximum proliferation rate over the whole simulation area, using second order polynomials (with negative second derivative) for the environmental covariate effects, with the exception of the spawner density in scenario 2 which was obtained as a function of the intercept and of the spatiotemporal random effect only.

For last, given the environmental covariates, and model parameters, we simulated a random realization of fisheries catch data and fish larval data from the observation models (Section 3.4). We fitted the spatially explicit annual population growth model to each of the simulated data by running four MCMC chains using Stan. We then checked for the convergence of the chains and retained only those model runs (and the respective simulated data) for which the Rhat summary statistics did not indicate convergence problems. This resulted in 50 simulation studies for each of the three scenarios.

4 Extra results from the whitefish case study

4.1 Posterior predictive check of the models

The posterior predictive check for the spatially explicit Ricker reproduction model under the zero-inflated formulation is visualized in Figure A.2. The posterior predictive checks for the other models were qualitatively similar, none showing significant deviations between the observed and predicted distribution of data.

4.2 Posterior distributions for parameters of compared models

The posterior distributions for the spatially explicit population growth models (excluding the covariate effects (β) and hyperparameters) are summarized in table A.1 and Figure A.3 for the zero-inflated and in table A.2 and Figure A.4 for the hurdle formulation. The posterior distributions for the parameters (excluding the covariate effects (β) and hyperparameters) of the species distribution models are summarized in tables A.1 and A.2 and Figure A.5.

The comparison between the response curves along the covariates for the three processes of the spatially explicit reproduction models is shown in Figure A.6. Similar comparison between the response curves for the two processes in the zero-inflated and hurdle SDMs is shown in Figure A.7. In both of these figures, each curve in each plot corresponds to the posterior estimate, centered in 0, of one of the covariate multiplicative effect (plot column) on one of the latent processes (plot row), for a randomly selected MC sample from the posterior distribution, as the covariate increases over 100 values along its range. Different colors correspond to different models, as specified in the legend. The images show how zero-inflated models curves present more variability than the hurdle ones. The trends are similar overall, with the main differences visible in responses of 'distance to deep' and 'distance to sand' covariates.

Figure A.2: Comparison of the empirical distribution of the data y to the posterior predictive distributions of predicted data y_{rep} for sampled larvae abundance (A, C) and for the logarithm of the tons of catches (B, D, E), in terms of density (A-B), cumulative density (C-D) and probability integral transform (PIT) quantiles vs. the standard uniform quantiles (E) for the spatially explicit Ricker reproduction model under the zero-inflated formulation. PIT values for larvae observations are omitted, due to the difficulty of computing loo-PIT values for count data.

Table A.2: Posterior mean and 95% credible interval of the main parameters of the SDM and of the spatially explicit Ricker, Beverton-Holt, and density-independent larval production models under the hurdle formulation.

	SDM	Posterior mean (95% credible interval)		
		Ricker	Beverton-Holt	Density-independent
σ_ϵ	NA	0.3312 (0.0926 , 0.6307)	0.3239 (0.0578 , 0.6226)	0.3282 (0.0981 , 0.6179)
σ_δ	2.9054 (1.3055 , 5.5951)	2.9548 (0.6397 , 5.2764)	3.0241 (1.1639 , 5.2454)	2.9909 (1.2074 , 5.1606)
$\bar{\alpha}$	0.6441 (0.175 , 1.2441)	0.6957 (0.1912 , 1.2384)	0.6945 (0.2200 , 1.2937)	0.6880 (0.2169 , 1.2390)
\bar{a}	7.2872 (5.2813 , 9.3415)	8.6874 (6.8286 , 10.5599)	8.727 (6.7522 , 10.5239)	8.6982 (6.7673 , 10.5197)
r	0.0634 (0.0129 , 0.1397)	0.0350 (0.0033 , 0.0984)	0.0360 (0.0034 , 0.1278)	0.0339 (0.0043 , 0.0976)
l	253.7015 (27.5982 , 855.8279)	1164.7743 (100.8347 , 3504.5807)	1232.3988 (192.0932 , 3653.1405)	1191.3734 (182.185 , 3532.012)
α	NA	-0.2110 (-3.6059, 3.5668)	-0.2557 (-3.6708, 3.5229)	-0.2884 (-3.6561, 3.4864)
λ	NA	0.0200 (1e-04 , 0.0882)	0.0214 (7e-04 , 0.0904)	0.0208 (8e-04 , 0.0926)
b	NA	20.4965 (0.8324 , 70.6276)	20.1079 (0.8312 , 65.7270)	NA

Figure A.3: Prior vs posterior distribution histograms for the main parameters of the spatially explicit Ricker population growth model under the zero-inflated formulation.

Figure A.4: Prior vs posterior distribution histograms for the main parameters of the spatially explicit Ricker population growth model under the hurdle formulation.

Figure A.5: Prior vs posterior distribution histograms for the main parameters of the SDM under zero-inflated (ZI, first row) and hurdle (second row) formulation.

Figure A.6: Comparison of the response curves for the Ricker, Beverton-Holt, and density-independent spatially explicit reproduction models under the zero-inflated (ZI) and hurdle formulation. Each line represents one draw from the posterior distribution of the response curves. The curve is drawn along the focal covariate while keeping the other covariates at their average over sampling locations (i.e., at zero).

Figure A.7: Comparison of the response curves for the zero-inflated (ZI) and hurdle SDMs. Each line represents one draw from the posterior distribution of the response curves. The curve is drawn along the focal covariate while keeping the other covariates at their average over sampling locations (i.e., at zero).

References

- Boss, J., Datta, J., Wang, X., Park, S. K., Kang, J., and Mukherjee, B. (2023). Group inverse-gamma gamma shrinkage for sparse linear models with block-correlated regressors. *Bayesian Analysis*, -1(-1).
- Freeberg, M. H., Taylor, W. W., and Brown, R. W. (1990). Effect of egg and larval survival

Figure A.8: Predictive maps of coefficient of variation of spawning suitability, spawner density and maximum proliferation rate of the spatially explicit Ricker population growth model under the zero-inflated formulation.

Figure A.9: Sites suitability, expected abundance of larvae conditional on site being suitable, and the (unconditional) expected abundance of larvae as predicted by the zero-inflated SDM.

Figure A.10: A) Predictive maps from the spatially explicit Ricker model under the hurdle formulation: the posterior median of the suitability, spawner density, proliferation rate, and the expected larvae density along the Finnish coastal area of the Gulf of Bothnia (GoB). B) Posterior distribution for the fraction of suitable sites, the total spawner biomass, the total larval production in the three GoB subregions: the Bothnian Bay, the Quark, and the Bothnian Sea (see Figure 1.A)

- on year-class strength of lake whitefish in grand traverse bay, lake michigan. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society*, 119(1):92–100.
- Froese, R. and Pauly, D. (2023). Fishbase. www.fishbase.org. World Wide Web electronic publication. Accessed: 2023-08-17.
- Lehtonen, H. (1981). Biology and stock assessments of coregonids by the baltic coast of finland. *Finnish Fisheries Research*, 3:31–83.
- Li, C.-S. (2012). Identifiability of zero-inflated Poisson models. *Brazilian Journal of Probability and Statistics*, 26(3):306 – 312.
- Veneranta, L. and Harjunpää, H. (2017). Kokemäenjoen vaellussiika – kutualueet ja poikasten esiintyminen. Technical Report 27/2017, Natural Resources Institute Finland. Luonnonvara- ja biotalouden tutkimus.
- Veneranta, L., Hudd, R., and Vanhatalo, J. (2013). Reproduction areas of sea-spawning coregonids reflect the environment in shallow coastal waters. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 477:231–250.